

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-SUBSTITUTED-4-(*p*-METHOXY-PHENYL) PIPERIDINE-2,6-DIONES(IV)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %
IVa	4-Pyridyl	163-164	53
IVb	6-Methyl-2-pyridyl	182-183	43
IVc	3-Methyl-2-pyridyl	141-142	28
IVd	2-Pyrimidyl	176-177	33
IVe	4 Methyl-2-pyrimidyl	184-185	32
IVf	4,6-Dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl	207-208	34
IVg	-CH ₂ -COOH	167-168	71

Elemental analyses of the compound were consistent with their composition.

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Studies on Cycloimmonium Ylides : Synthesis of Some New 2,4,6-Triaryl Pyridines via Pyridinium Ylides

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IN continuation to our previous researches¹⁻² directed towards studies on pyridinium ylides, presently we wish to report herein the synthesis of some new 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines having phenyl, naphthyl

and phenanthryl ring attached to the pyridine nucleus which have been achieved by the cyclization reaction of 3-phenanthroylmethylene pyridinium ylide with α , β -unsaturated ketones.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallen Kamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer infracord spectrophotometer in KBr phase. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were run using A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The products were purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina. The purity was checked by thin layer chromatography using glass plates coated with silica gel 'G' and the spots were detected by placing the tlc plates in iodine chamber.

The pyridinium salt (1) was prepared using the procedure of King *et al*^{7,8}.

Preparation of 2,4,6-triaryl-substituted pyridines (5a-n) :

A mixture of pyridinium salt (1) (3 mmol) and ammonium acetate (3g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was stirred for 30 minutes. To this mixture benzylidene ketone (3a-n) (3 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), was added dropwise during 1 hr, after which the temperature was maintained at 120° and heating was continued for additional 4-8 hr. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and ice cold water (20 ml) was added to precipitate a solid which was separated, washed with methanol, dried and crystallized from appropriate solvent to give 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines (5a-n) in 40-75 percent yields (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

3-Phenanthroylmethyl pyridinium salt (1) reacts with a variety of substituted benzylideneacetophenones (3a-e), benzylidene 2-acetonaphthalenes (3f-i) and benzylidene 3-acetophenanthrenes (3j-n) in the presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid at reflux temperature to give 2,4-di-(substitutedphenyl)-6-(3-phenanthryl)pyridines (5a-e), 4-substitutedphenyl-2-naphthyl-6-(3-phenanthryl) pyridines (5f-i) and 2,6-di-(3-phenanthryl)-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridines (5j-n) in 40-75 percent yields (Scheme-1).

The course of formation of pyridines from pyridinium ylide has been reported earlier^{3,4}. The ylide (2), which was supposed to be formed by the dehydrohalogenation of pyridinium salt (1), attack on β -carbon atom of α , β -unsaturated ketones (3a-n), yielding new ylide intermediate, pentane-1,5-dionyl pyridinium derivatives (4) which, in turn, underwent cyclization in the presence of ammonium acetate to give 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyridines (5a-n).

The pyridines (5a-n) thus synthesized gave satisfactory elemental analysis and were new. The IR spectra (KBr) showed a characteristic absorption

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2,4,6-TRIARYL PYRIDINES (5a-n)

Compd.*	m.p. °C	Recrystn. solvent	Yield	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃) data**			IR (KBr) data cm ⁻¹		
				δ ppm	No. of protons	Assignment	C=C Stretching	C=N Stretching	C-H Stretching
5a	156-58	Py-MeOH	65	7.17-8.73m 2.48s	19H 3H	Aromatic Methyl			
5b	140-41	CHCl ₃ -MeOH	60	6.82-8.40m 2.45s	18H 3H	Aromatic methyl			
5c	108-10	Py-MeOH	65	—	—	—	1595	1503	3021
5d	142-44	Py-CHCl ₃	75	6.83-8.55m 6.06s	18H 2H	Aromatic -OCH ₂ -O-			
5e	180-82	CHCl ₃ -MeOH	55	—	—	—	1600	1546	3020
5f	178-80	Py-MeOH	65	—	—	—	1600	1570	3090
5g	135-37	CHCl ₃ -MeOH	60	7.07-8.21m	21H	Aromatic	1597	1558	3125
5h	170-72	Py-EtOH	55	6.73-8.66m 3.85d (J=4.5 Hz)	20H 6H	Aromatic Dimethoxy	—	—	—
5i	170-72	Py-MeOH	50	7.80-8.44m 2.47s	22H 3H	Aromatic Methyl	—	—	—
5j	150-55	CHCl ₃ -MeOH]	50	7.20-8.43m 4.03s	24H 3H	Aromatic Methoxy	—	—	—
5k	107-09	Py-EtOH	60	7.50-8.44m 2.40s	24H 3H	Aromatic Methyl	—	—	—
5l	220-22	CHCl ₃ -MeOH	60	6.87-8.64m 6.03s	23H 2H	Aromatic -OCH ₂ O-	1592	1548	3058
5m	180-82	Py-EtOH	30	—	—	—	1615	1550	3140
5n	230-34	Py-MeOH	40	—	—	—	1608	1546	3006

* All compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C, H and N.

** Key words : s=singlet, m=multiplet, d=doublet.

band in the region 3100-3000 cm⁻¹, which was assigned to the C-H stretching mode of the pyridine rings. Two bands in the region 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1500 cm⁻¹ were assigned to the C=C and C=N

vibrations of the pyridine rings. The former band appearing as a double absorption maxima near 1600 cm⁻¹ seems to be a general characteristic of trisubstitution at pyridine nucleus^{5,6}. The nmr

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| 1, 2, R ¹ = 3-phenanthryl; | R ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ |
| 3, 4, 5a, R ¹ = 3-phenanthryl; | R ² = 2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ ; | R ³ = 4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ |
| b, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄ |
| c, R ¹ = " | R ² = 3,4-O ₂ CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ ; | R ³ = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄ |
| d, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄ |
| e, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄ |
| f, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 2-C ₁₀ H ₇ |
| g, R ¹ = " | R ² = 2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ ; | R ³ = 2-C ₁₀ H ₇ |
| h, R ¹ = " | R ² = 3,4-(OCH ₂) ₂ ; | R ³ = 2-C ₁₀ H ₇ |
| | 6-Br.C ₆ H ₃ ; | |
| i, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 2-C ₁₀ H ₇ |
| j, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-OCH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = 3-phenanthryl |
| k, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = " |
| l, R ¹ = " | R ² = 3,4-O ₂ CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ ; | R ³ = " |
| m, R ¹ = " | R ² = 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ ; | R ³ = " |
| n, R ¹ = " | R ² = 2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ ; | R ³ = " |

spectra (CDCl_3) in general showed aromatic multiplets in the range δ 6.80 - .60 (Table 1).

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Synthesis of Some Pyrimidinylpyrazoles and Pyrimidinyl-2-Pyrazoline-5-Ones

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PYRAZOLES are known to possess various types of biological activity¹⁻³. Arylazo derivatives of pyrazoles have been prepared earlier in these laboratories as possible antidiabetic agents^{4,5}. In view of the important pharmacological activity displayed by the pyrimidine derivatives, it was thought of considerable interest to prepare the compounds containing both the pyrimidine and pyrazole nucleus. The present communication describes the synthesis of various 3,5-disubstituted-1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-4-arylazopyrazoles (I, II and III) and 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3-methyl-4-arylhydrazono-2-pyrazoline-5-ones (IV).

The condensation of 2-hydrazino-4,6-dimethylpyrimidine⁶ with 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones⁴, 1-phenylbutane-1,2,3-trione-2-arylhydrazones⁷ and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,2,3-trione-2-arylhydrazones in glacial acetic acid-ethanol gave 1-(4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazoles(I). (Table 1),

TABLE 1 - 4-ARYLAZO-(4,6-DIMETHYL PYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3,5-DIMETHYL-PYRAZOLES(I)

[I], $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$,
[II], $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$,
[III], $R_1 = R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$,

Compound No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C
1	Hydrogen	50	98 ^a
2	2-Chloro	65	142 ^d
3	3-Chloro	65	112 ^c
4	2-Methyl	60	150 ^d
5	4-Methyl	70	160 ^b
6	2-Methoxy	55	136 ^d
7	2-Ethoxy	60	178 ^c
8	4-Ethoxy	60	89 ^d
9	4-Bromo	70	114 ^f
10	2,5-Dimethyl	70	142 ^d
11	3-Nitro	65	108 ^d

a, red; b, light yellow; c, yellow; d, brown; e, orange yellow; f, light greenish yellow.

The nitrogen analysis of all the compounds is consistent with the respective composition.

TABLE 2 - 4-ARYLAZO-1-(4,6-DIMETHYLPYRIMIDIN-2-YL)-3-METHYL-5-PHENYLPYRAZOLES(II)

Compound No.	R	Yield %	mp. °C
1	Hydrogen	70	154
2	2-Chloro	60	207 ^e
3	3-Chloro	55	170 ^c
4	2-Methyl	50	155 ^e
5	2-Methoxy	50	208 ^c
6	3-Methoxy	45	142 ^d
7	4-Ethoxy	55	120 ^d
8	2,3-Dimethyl	60	267 ^d
9	2,5-Dimethyl	60	110 ^d
10	2,5-Dichloro	65	178 ^c

* See footnote Table 1.